

Electronic Supporting Information for:

Green Colloidal Synthesis of MoS₂ Nanoflakes

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S1. Precursors toxicity characteristics

As the criteria for the extent of toxicity of the precursors, we used the information on the lethal dose, in-vivo and environmental toxicity, published by the European Chemical Agency (ECHA).³³

The information is summarized tables S1-S3. The known lethal doses shown in the Table S1 are given in mg/kg and lethal concentrations in mg/L, based on tests on rats.

For in-vivo studies, a brief description of categories is:

Carcinogenicity: Category 1A (Known to induce heritable mutations in germ cells of humans), Category 1B (Substances which should be regarded as if they induce heritable mutations in the germ cells of humans), Category 2 (Concern for human owing to the possibility that they may induce heritable mutation in germ cells of humans).

Skin corrosion: Category 1 (Visible destruction of skin tissue in at least one tested animal after exposure \leq 4h), Category 1A (Corrosive responses in at least one animal following exposure \leq 3 min during an observation period \leq 1 h), Category 1B (Corrosive responses in at least one animal following exposure 3 min – 1 h during an observation period \leq 14 days), Category 1C (Corrosive responses in at least one animal following exposure 1 h – 4 h during an observation period \leq 14 days), Category 2 (Irritation of skin), Category 3 (Mild irritation).

Eye damage: Category 1 (serious eye damage/irreversible effect on the eye), Category 2 (eye irritation/reversible effects on the eye).

Specific target organ toxicity: Category 1 (Substances that have produced significant toxicity in humans, or that, on the basis of evidence from studies in experimental animals can be presumed to have the potential to produce significant toxicity in humans following single exposure), Category 2 (Substances that, on the basis of evidence from studies in experimental animals can

be presumed to have the potential to be harmful to human health following single exposure), Category 3 (Transient target organ effects).

In terms of the **environmental toxicity**, the brief description of categories: Both short-term (acute) and long-term (chronological) aquatic hazards are measured as lethal concentration LC₅₀ for fish, effective concentration EC₅₀ for crustacea or effective concentration resulting in the reduction of growth rate ErC₅₀ for algae. Acute toxicity: Category I (≤1 mg/L), Category II (1-10 mg/L) and Category III (10-100 mg/L).

Table S1. Lethal doses and concentrations of investigated precursors.

Precursor	Oral [mg/kg]	Dermal [mg/kg]	Vapour Inhalation [mg/L]	Dust and mist Inhalation [mg/L]
[Mo(CO) ₆]	–	–	–	–
[Mo ₂ (CH ₃ CO) ₄]	–	–	–	–
MoCl ₅	–	–	–	–
CS ₂	>2000	–	10.35	–
HMDS	100	300	3	–
TAA	301	–	–	–
3-MPA	96	–	–	1.81
L-CYS	5850	>2000	–	–
MSA	800	–	–	–
MUA	–	–	–	–
DDTH	>5000	>2000	>3.1	–
DTBD	–	–	–	–

Table S2. In-vivo toxicity of investigated precursors.

Precursor	Carcinogenicity	Skin corrosion	Eye damage	Specific target organ toxicity
[Mo(CO) ₆]	–	–	–	–
[Mo ₂ (CH ₃ CO) ₄]	–	–	–	–
MoCl ₅	–	(Sub-category 1B)	(Category 1)	–
CS ₂	–	(Category 2)	(Category 2)	(Category 2) Respiratory system Reproduction system
HMDS	–	–	–	–
TAA	(Category 1B)	(Category 2)	(Category 2)	–
3-MPA	–	(Sub-category 1B)	(Category 1)	–
L-CYS	–	–	–	–
MSA	–	(Category 2)	(Category 2)	(Category 3) Respiratory system
MUA	–	(Category 2)	(Category 2)	(Category 3)

				Respiratory system
DDTH	–	(Sub-category 1C)	(Category 1)	–
DTBD	–	–	–	–

Table S3. Environmental toxicity of investigated precursors.

Precursor	Short-term aquatic hazard	Long-term aquatic hazard
[Mo(CO) ₆]	–	–
[Mo ₂ (CH ₃ CO) ₄]	–	–
MoCl ₅	–	–
CS ₂	–	(Category 3)
HMDS	–	–
TAA	–	(Category 3)
3-MPA	–	–
L-CYS	–	–
MSA	–	–
MUA	–	–
DDTH	(Category 1)	(Category 1)
DTBD	–	(Category 2)

S2. Supporting TEM results

HAADF-STEM image simulation was done by software JEMS.^[70] The input parameters were set according to the experimental conditions of the microscope, *i.e.*, accelerating voltage, convergence angle, and inner and outer angles of ADF detector. In addition, the energy spread and virtual source size were set to 0.4 eV and 50 nm, respectively. To simplify the calculation, multi-slice simulation was carried out with the frozen lattice approximation at 0K.

Figure S1. Experimental unprocessed HAADF-STEM image and corresponding line profile (along blue rectangle) of the MoS₂ product prepared using 3-MPA precursor (a); and multi-slice STEM simulation of MoS₂ structure using Jems software (b).[ref. 70 in the main text]

Figure S2. HAADF-STEM image of the MoS₂ NF product prepared using MUA. Line intensity profiles (LP1, LP2, LP3) taken across different NF flakes. The interlayer spacing was found to be between 11 to 19 Å.

Figure S3. EELS analysis of the MoS₂ NF product prepared using 3-MPA. HAADF image (a), Mo map (b), S map (c) and corresponding EELS spectrum (d) showing S and Mo core edges.

S3. Supporting GIWAXS results

Figure S4. GIWAXS pattern of MoS₂ flakes prepared by following precursors a) 3-mercaptopropionic acid (3-MPA), b) di-tert-butyl disulfide (DTBD), c) mercaptoundecanoic acid (MUA), d) L-cysteine (L-CYS), e) thioacetamide (TAA), f) 1-dodecanethiol (DDTH).

S4. AFM analysis

Figure S5 shows the results of the AFM study of the MoS₂ nanoflakes prepared by using mercapto-succinic acid (MSA) as the S-precursor, compared with the analysis of the corresponding substrate. The results indicate the presence of structures with the height of ~0.9 - 1 nm and width of ~15 - 20 nm. The observed height is consistent with the previously measured height for a single-layer MoS₂ on Si substrate, with typical observed range ~0.8 - 1 nm.^[S1-S5] The reported thickness of the double layer of MoS₂ is ~1.4 - 1.6 nm.^[S6-S8] The width of the nanostructures is consistent with the STEM results summarized in the main text.

Figure S5. (a) Results of the Atomic Force Microcopy (AFM) measurement of the MoS₂ nanoflakes prepared by using mercapto-succinic acid (MSA) as the S-precursor. (b). Analysis of the topography. (c) Control AFM measurement of the blank substrate. (d) Analysis of the topography of the blank substrate. For the analysis, the solution of MoS₂ nanoflakes was spin-coated from *n*-hexane solution onto a silicon substrate with a native layer of SiO₂. AFM scan was performed by HR-AFM, Multimode 8 (BrukerNano). Scan area is 400 x 400 nm with resolution of 1 nm.

References

- S1. Li, H., Zhang, Q., Yap, C. C. R., Tay, B. K., Edwin, T. H. T., Olivier, A., & Baillargeat, D. From bulk to monolayer MoS₂: evolution of Raman scattering. *Adv. Funct. Mat.*, **2012**, 22(7), 1385-1390.
- S2. Zhang, H., Ma, Y., Wan, Y., Rong, X., Xie, Z., Wang, W., & Dai, L. Measuring the refractive index of highly crystalline monolayer MoS₂ with high confidence. *Sci. Rep.*, **2015**, 5(1), 8440.
- S3. Xiao, X., Li, J., Wu, J., Lu, D., & Tang, C. Negative photoconductivity observed in polycrystalline monolayer molybdenum disulfide prepared by chemical vapor deposition. *Appl. Phys. A*, **2019**, 125, 1-7.
- S4. Li, Y., Yu, C., Gan, Y., Jiang, P., Yu, J., Ou, Y. & Li, J. Mapping the elastic properties of two-dimensional MoS₂ via bimodal atomic force microscopy and finite element simulation. *NPJ Comp. Mat.*, **2018**, 4(1), 49.
- S5. Lanzillo, N. A., Glen Birdwell, A., Amani, M., Crowne, F. J., Shah, P. B., Najmaei, S., O'Regan, T. P. Temperature-dependent phonon shifts in monolayer MoS₂. *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, **2013**, 103(9).
- S6. Yu, Y., Li, C., Liu, Y., Su, L., Zhang, Y., & Cao, L. Controlled scalable synthesis of uniform, high-quality monolayer and few-layer MoS₂ films. *Sci. Rep.*, **2013**, 3(1), 1866.
- S7. Lee, Y. H., Zhang, X. Q., Zhang, W., Chang, M. T., Lin, C. T., Chang, K. D. & Lin, T. W. Synthesis of large-area MoS₂ atomic layers with chemical vapor deposition. *Adv. Mat.*, **2012**, 24(17), 2320-2325.
- S8. Mukherjee, S., Maiti, R., Katiyar, A. K., Das, S., & Ray, S. K. Novel colloidal MoS₂ quantum dot heterojunctions on silicon platforms for multifunctional optoelectronic devices. *Sci. Rep.*, **2016**, 6(1), 29016.